

ADAPTIVE NULLING FOR MULTIPLE DESIRED SIGNALS BASED ON SIGNAL WAVEFORM ESTIMATION

Kristine Bell*, John Capetanakis*, and Jeffrey Bugler†

*George Mason University, Fairfax, Virginia 22030-4444

†Joint Interoperability and Engineering Organization / Center for Engineering, Reston, Virginia 22090-5500

Abstract

In this paper we consider adaptive nulling of noise and interference in the presence of multiple desired signals. We reformulate the adaptive nulling problem as a signal estimation problem and derive several adaptive nulling algorithms which require varying amounts of a priori information about the desired signals. The a priori information required by the algorithms may include signal directions-of-arrival, relative power levels, and/or probability density functions for signal DOA's when they are not known exactly. Furthermore, we show that the optimal signal estimators derived are equivalent to the classical adaptive nulling techniques of Howells-Applebaum, LMS, and Frost when supplied with certain a priori information, and that in several cases, the resulting expressions for the optimal weights have forms to which well known adaptation procedures can be readily applied.

I. INTRODUCTION

Consider a communications system which must simultaneously receive several desired signals from spatially distributed sources in the presence of undesired interference signals and receiver noise. An example of such a system is a direction finding and listening system. Another example is a satellite which receives, amplifies, and retransmits the signals to their final destination. In these systems, the probability of correctly demodulating the desired signals can be improved by using an adaptive antenna array in the initial receiver. The array enhances the desired signals while suppressing the interferers and noise by forming an antenna gain pattern with high gain in the directions of the desired signals and low gain, or nulls, in the directions of the interferers.

The general form of an adaptive antenna array is shown in Figure 1. The beamformer consists of multiple antenna elements whose outputs are multiplied by a set of weights (or more generally passed through a set of filters) and summed to form a single output signal. The values of the weights (filters) applied to each element control the gain pattern of the antenna. By weighting (filtering) each element differently, the overall gain pattern and frequency response can be tailored to suit system requirements. In this paper, we consider adaptive nulling of narrowband signals centered about a known frequency, and assume that the signals have a sufficiently narrow bandwidth that the optimal filters for each element can be approximated by a single weight followed by a narrow bandpass filter.

The adaptive processor computes the optimum filter weights required to null interferers while enhancing desired signals. The inputs to the processor include the received signals at the outputs of the elements, the final "adapted" signal, and some a priori information about the desired signals. The a priori information

Figure 1. Adaptive Nulling System

may include desired signal directions-of-arrival (DOA), waveform characteristics, etc. The element outputs contain all the information available to the processor about the actual environment (i.e. desired signals, interferers, and noise). The a priori information is used to distinguish desired signals from interferers, and the adapted output is the feedback that provides a measure of how well the system is doing. The adaptive processor extracts the necessary information from these inputs and computes the optimum weights for the current environment.

Adaptive nulling has been studied since the late 1960's [1-7] and many techniques have been developed which use different optimization criteria to compute the optimum weights. They also use different a priori information and processing techniques, and in general produce different weights (and therefore different gain patterns). The majority of the algorithms developed to date are variations on a few classical techniques summarized below.

The Howells-Applebaum (H-A) algorithm [2-4] computes optimum weights for the beamformer by maximizing the desired signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR), where the noise includes both white noise and interferers. It was developed for the case when there is only one desired signal present, and uses a "steering vector" to steer the gain pattern in the direction of the desired signal, therefore requiring signal DOA information. The H-A algorithm can be used with multiple desired signals by modifying the steering vector to steer the gain pattern in the directions of multiple signals. In this case, the optimal weights minimize the noise while maintaining "closeness" to the steering vector, and may or may not maximize SNR.

This work was supported by DISA JIEO / CFE.

38.5.1

U.S. Government work not protected by U.S. copyright

0919

The Least-Mean-Square (LMS) algorithm (developed by Widrow et. al. [5]) computes the optimum weights for the beamformer by minimizing the mean squared error between the output signal and a reference signal. It also was developed for the case of only one desired signal, and the reference signal is chosen to have some common characteristic with the desired signal. This technique can be extended to multiple signals in one of two ways. One reference signal can be used, provided all the signals are correlated with the reference signal (and therefore with each other). A difficulty arises in using this method in a communications application in that the desired signals are generally designed to be mutually uncorrelated so that each may be separated from the others prior to demodulation. Alternately, separate reference signals can be used for each of the desired signals, however implementation of this method can become impractical if there are a great many desired signals.

The Frost algorithm [6] computes the optimum weights which minimize the antenna output power while constraining the gain in the directions of the desired signals to be fixed. This technique is readily used with multiple desired signals and requires signal DOA information.

In addition to the problems encountered when applying the H-A and LMS techniques to multiple desired signals, each of these techniques uses a particular type of a priori information (DOA or waveform structure) which is assumed to be known exactly. When some or all of the DOA's or waveforms are unknown, these techniques cannot be used. Furthermore, none of the methods allows for incorporating more than one type of a priori information. In this paper, we reformulate the adaptive nulling problem as a waveform estimation problem, and derive the weight vector which produces the optimal estimate of a linear combination of the desired signals. This formulation allows more flexibility in incorporating a priori knowledge, and the beamformer weights derived are the same as those of the classical nulling techniques when the same a priori information is used. The focus of this paper is on obtaining expressions for the final "adapted" weights and not on the adaptation procedures, however, many of the resulting expressions for the optimal weights have forms to which well known adaptation techniques can be applied.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

In the following, we use lower case bold letters for vectors, uppercase bold letters for matrices, * to denote the complex-conjugate, ^T to denote the transpose, and ^H to denote the complex-conjugate (or Hermitian) transpose.

A. Definitions

The antenna array in the beamformer has M elements, or sensors, which receive radiation from narrowband sources, p of which are desired signals and q of which are interferers. We assume that the number of desired and interference signals is less than the number of sensors (p+q<M) in order to guarantee the uniqueness of the optimum weight vector. The radiation from the kth source impinges on the array in the form of a plane wave from direction θ_k , and the received signal at each element consists of narrowband source signals plus noise, which are all centered about a known center frequency f_0 . The complex envelope of the received signal at the ith sensor at time t is given by:

$$x_i(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{p+q} a_i(\theta_k) s_k(t) + n_i(t) \quad (1)$$

where $a_i(\theta_k)$ = the response of the ith sensor to a signal from direction θ_k ,
 $s_k(t)$ = the kth source waveform (desired or interference),
 $n_i(t)$ = additive noise at the ith sensor.

Employing vector notation, the Mx1 vector of received signals can be expressed as a sum of a desired signal term, an interference signal term, and a noise term:

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{p+q} \mathbf{a}(\theta_k) s_k(t) + \mathbf{n}(t) = \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D) \mathbf{s}_D(t) + \mathbf{A}(\Theta_I) \mathbf{s}_I(t) + \mathbf{n}(t) \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{where } \mathbf{x}(t) &= [x_1(t) \dots x_M(t)]^T, \\ \mathbf{a}(\theta_k) &= [a_1(\theta_k) \dots a_M(\theta_k)]^T, \\ \Theta_D &= [\theta_1 \dots \theta_p]^T, \\ \Theta_I &= [\theta_{p+1} \dots \theta_{p+q}]^T, \\ \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D) &= [\mathbf{a}(\theta_1) \dots \mathbf{a}(\theta_p)], \\ \mathbf{A}(\Theta_I) &= [\mathbf{a}(\theta_{p+1}) \dots \mathbf{a}(\theta_{p+q})], \\ \mathbf{s}_D(t) &= [s_1(t) \dots s_p(t)]^T, \\ \mathbf{s}_I(t) &= [s_{p+1}(t) \dots s_{p+q}(t)]^T, \\ \mathbf{n}(t) &= [n_1(t) \dots n_M(t)]^T. \end{aligned}$$

The received signals are multiplied by complex weights and summed to form the output signal of the beamformer:

$$y(t) = \sum_{i=1}^M w_i^* x_i(t) = \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{x}(t). \quad (3)$$

The source signals may be deterministic functions or sample functions of stationary and ergodic stochastic processes. In either case, we assume that all the signals are mutually uncorrelated. The desired and interference correlation matrices can be defined as:

(ii) Stochastic

$$\mathbf{R}_D \equiv E\{\mathbf{s}_D(t) \mathbf{s}_D^H(t)\}; \quad \mathbf{R}_I \equiv E\{\mathbf{s}_I(t) \mathbf{s}_I^H(t)\}. \quad (4a)$$

(i) Deterministic

$$\mathbf{R}_D \equiv \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T \mathbf{s}_D(t) \mathbf{s}_D^H(t) dt; \quad \mathbf{R}_I \equiv \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T \mathbf{s}_I(t) \mathbf{s}_I^H(t) dt. \quad (4b)$$

They will be diagonal matrices whose non-zero entries are equal to the average received power of the corresponding signals.

The noise is a stationary and ergodic complex-valued, zero-mean, white Gaussian process with known covariance:

$$\mathbf{R}_w \equiv E\{\mathbf{n}(t) \mathbf{n}^H(t)\} = \sigma^2 \mathbf{I} \quad (5)$$

where σ^2 is the noise power. Thus, the noise is uncorrelated in both space and time. Furthermore, we assume that the source signals and noise are uncorrelated at all times. Under these assumptions, the correlation matrix of the received signals can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R}_x &\equiv E\{\mathbf{x}(t) \mathbf{x}^H(t)\} = \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D) \mathbf{R}_D \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D)^H + \mathbf{A}(\Theta_I) \mathbf{R}_I \mathbf{A}(\Theta_I)^H + \sigma^2 \mathbf{I} \\ &= \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D) \mathbf{R}_D \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D)^H + \mathbf{R}_n, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\mathbf{R}_n = \mathbf{A}(\Theta_I) \mathbf{R}_I \mathbf{A}(\Theta_I)^H + \sigma^2 \mathbf{I} \quad (7)$$

is the correlation matrix of the interference plus white noise.

38.5.2

B. Classical Nulling Algorithms

For a single desired signal from direction θ_s , the Howells-Applebaum optimum weight vector which maximizes the output SNR is found from:

$$\mathbf{w} = \arg \max_{\mathbf{w}} \frac{|\mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{a}(\theta_s)|^2}{\mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{R}_n \mathbf{w}} \quad (8)$$

and is given by:

$$\mathbf{w} = \mu \mathbf{R}_n^{-1} \mathbf{a}(\theta_s) \quad (9)$$

where μ is an arbitrary constant. When there is more than one signal, the H-A weights maximize a generalized SNR given by:

$$\mathbf{w} = \arg \max_{\mathbf{w}} \frac{|\mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{t}|^2}{\mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{R}_n \mathbf{w}} \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{t} is the "generalized signal vector" or "steering vector" which steers the beam in the directions of the desired signals. The optimum weight vector for this problem is:

$$\mathbf{w} = \mu \mathbf{R}_n^{-1} \mathbf{t} \quad (11)$$

Although the optimal H-A weight vectors are given by Equations (9) and (11), the H-A control loop which determines the optimum weights actually computes:

$$\mathbf{w} = \mu \mathbf{R}_x^{-1} \mathbf{t} \quad (12)$$

with \mathbf{R}_x replacing \mathbf{R}_n . However, when there is only one desired signal and $\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{a}(\theta_s)$, Equations (11) and (12) are equivalent to within a multiplicative constant.

The LMS algorithm minimizes the mean square error between the desired signals and a reference signal and the optimum weights are given by:

$$\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{R}_x^{-1} \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D) \rho_{rs} \quad (13)$$

where $\rho_{rs} = E\{r(t) s_D(t)\}$ is the correlation between the reference signal and the desired signals.

The Frost algorithm minimizes the total output power subject to the constraints that the amplitude response of the beamformer in the directions of the desired signals is fixed, i.e.

$$\mathbf{w} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{w}} \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{R}_x \mathbf{w} \quad \text{subject to} \quad \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D)^H \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{c} \quad (14)$$

and the optimum weights are given by:

$$\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{R}_x^{-1} \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D) \left(\mathbf{A}(\Theta_D)^H \mathbf{R}_x^{-1} \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D) \right)^{-1} \mathbf{c} \quad (15)$$

When there is only one desired signal, it is straightforward to show that the Howells-Applebaum, LMS, and Frost optimal weight vectors are identical to within a scale factor.

C. Waveform Estimation

Our objective is to find the weights which provide the best estimate of a linear combination of the desired signals, i.e. we wish to estimate:

$$\mathbf{g}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^P c_k s_k(t) = \mathbf{c}^H \mathbf{s}_D(t) \quad (16)$$

The estimator must be a (spatially) linear estimator of the form $\hat{\mathbf{g}}(t) = \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{x}(t)$, therefore the estimator uses only the current values of the received signals and none of their past values. This form is equivalent to passing the received signals through a bank of temporal filters whose frequency responses are constant for all frequencies, and is optimal only if the received signals are white

processes. In the actual beamformer, however, the weights are followed by narrowband filters which are not explicitly included in the problem formulation, but which provide the necessary temporal filtering. Thus, we will obtain optimal estimators of the correct form if we assume that the source signals are white and remember that we have suppressed the temporal filtering.

III. ESTIMATOR-NULLERS

In this section we derive the beamformer weights which provide optimal signal estimates under different assumptions. The different estimators yield weight vectors which require different types of a priori information, and the choice of estimator for a particular application will depend on the knowledge available about the signals. We first assume that desired signal DOA's and covariance matrix (i.e., received power levels) are known and derive the minimum mean square error (MMSE) and maximum a posteriori probability (MAP) estimators, as well as a constrained MMSE estimator, for which we assume that the source signals are sample functions of independent white Gaussian random processes. We also derive a maximum likelihood (ML) estimator, for which we do not assume Gaussian processes. Next we assume that the DOA's and covariances are unknown or partially known non-random parameters. In this case we must estimate the unknown parameters from training data and substitute the estimates into the optimal (informed) signal estimators. Finally we assume that the DOA's and covariances are unknown random variables whose a priori probability density functions are known, for which we present an MMSE and an MAP estimator.

A.1. MMSE/MAP - KNOWN DOA's & COVARIANCE

We assume that the source signals are sample functions of independent, zero-mean, white Gaussian random processes, and that the desired signal DOA's, Θ_D , and covariance matrix, \mathbf{R}_D , are known. Under these assumptions, the received signal vector, $\mathbf{x}(t)$, is a zero-mean, Gaussian random vector with covariance \mathbf{R}_x . The MMSE estimator of $\mathbf{g}(t)$ is the conditional mean:

$$\hat{\mathbf{g}}(t) = E[\mathbf{g}(t)|\mathbf{x}(t); 0 \leq u \leq t] = E[\mathbf{g}(t)|\mathbf{x}(t)] = \mathbf{c}^H E[\mathbf{s}_D(t)|\mathbf{x}(t)] \quad (17)$$

which has the form:

$$\hat{\mathbf{g}}(t) = \mathbf{c}^H \mathbf{R}_D \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D)^H \mathbf{R}_x^{-1} \mathbf{x}(t) \quad (18)$$

This is also the MAP estimate of $\mathbf{g}(t)$, since the maximum of the a posteriori density occurs at the mean. Thus, the optimal MMSE/MAP signal estimator is linear and the beamformer weights are given by:

$$\mathbf{w}_{MM} = \mathbf{R}_x^{-1} \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D) \mathbf{R}_D \mathbf{c} \quad (19)$$

This formulation is very similar to that used to derive the LMS weights, therefore, the resulting weight vector has the same form as the LMS version (13) with ρ_{rs} replaced by $\mathbf{R}_D \mathbf{c}$. The MMSE/MAP weights are also identical to the H-A weights (12) when the H-A steering vector is chosen so that $\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D) \mathbf{R}_D \mathbf{c}$ (i.e., the steering vector is a sum of the array response vectors in each of the desired signal directions, weighted by the received signal power and desired amplification).

To compute the optimal MMSE/MAP weights, knowledge of the desired signal DOA's and covariance matrix (received power levels) is required, as well as the covariance matrix of the received signals. \mathbf{R}_x is not generally known but may be derived from the received signals in a number of ways. It may be estimated adaptively in an "open-loop" manner from samples of the received signals using the standard sample covariance estimate:

$$\hat{\mathbf{R}}_x = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \mathbf{x}(t_n) \mathbf{x}^H(t_n) \quad (20)$$

or any other suitable estimate. Alternatively, the entire weight vector may be computed adaptively in a "closed-loop" fashion numerically [7,8] or by using a hardware control loop [2-4]. The latter two standard adaptation procedures include an implicit estimation of \mathbf{R}_x .

A. 2. CONSTRAINED MMSE - KNOWN DOA's

The MMSE/MAP estimator derived in the previous section required knowledge of the covariance (received power levels) of the desired signals. In this section we derive a (suboptimal) MMSE estimator which does not require this information. Suppose that we desire a linear MMSE estimator in which the gain in the directions of the desired signals is fixed, i.e., we desire the weight vector which minimizes the mean square error between $g(t) = \mathbf{c}^H \mathbf{s}_D(t)$ and $\hat{g}(t) = \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{x}(t)$ subject to the constraint that $\mathbf{A}(\Theta_D)^H \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{c}$, i.e.:

$$\mathbf{w} = \arg \min \mathbb{E} [|g(t) - \hat{g}(t)|^2] = \mathbb{E} [| \mathbf{c}^H \mathbf{s}_D(t) - \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{x}(t) |^2] \quad (21)$$

subject to $\mathbf{A}(\Theta_D)^H \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{c}$.

After some rearranging, the problem reduces to

$$\mathbf{w} = \arg \min \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{R}_x \mathbf{w} \quad \text{subject to } \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D)^H \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{c} \quad (22)$$

which is the problem posed by Frost [6] and whose solution is:

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{CM}} = \mathbf{R}_x^{-1} \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D) (\mathbf{A}(\Theta_D)^H \mathbf{R}_x^{-1} \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D))^{-1} \mathbf{c}. \quad (23)$$

Therefore the constrained MMSE estimate of $g(t)$ is given by:

$$\hat{g}(t) = \mathbf{c}^H (\mathbf{A}(\Theta_D)^H \mathbf{R}_x^{-1} \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D))^{-1} \mathbf{A}(\Theta_D)^H \mathbf{R}_x^{-1} \mathbf{x}(t). \quad (24)$$

The constrained MMSE estimator produces weights which are identical to the Frost weights, and which require knowledge of desired signal DOA's, but not their covariances (received power levels). The received signal covariance matrix also appears in the equation, and it may be estimated adaptively from the received signal samples as described above, or the weight vector may be computed adaptively, either numerically or in hardware [6,8].

A. 3. MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD - KNOWN DOA's

The previous estimators assumed that the source signals were white Gaussian random processes. We now change our assumptions somewhat, and assume that both the desired and interference signals have unknown, non-random waveforms, and that all the DOA's are known (including the interference DOA's). We can compute the ML estimator of $g(t)$, which is the weighted sum of the ML estimators of all the signals (both desired and interference):

$$\hat{g}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_k \hat{s}_k(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{p+q} \tilde{\alpha}_k \tilde{s}_k(t) = \tilde{\mathbf{c}}^H \tilde{\mathbf{s}}(t). \quad (25)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{c}}$ is a $(p+q) \times 1$ vector whose first p components are identical to the components of the vector \mathbf{c} and whose last q components are zeros, and $\mathbf{s}(t) = [\mathbf{s}_D(t)^T \mathbf{s}_I(t)^T]^T$. Under this formulation, the received signal vector, $\mathbf{x}(t)$, is a Gaussian random vector with mean $\mathbf{A}(\Theta) \mathbf{s}(t)$ and covariance $\sigma^2 \mathbf{I}$, where $\Theta = [\Theta_D^T \Theta_I^T]^T$. Its probability density function is given by:

$$p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}) = \frac{1}{\pi \det[\sigma^2 \mathbf{I}]} \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{\sigma^2} | \mathbf{x}(t) - \mathbf{A}(\Theta) \mathbf{s}(t) |^2 \right\} \quad (26)$$

and the log-likelihood function (excluding constant terms) is:

$$L = - | \mathbf{x}(t) - \mathbf{A}(\Theta) \mathbf{s}(t) |^2. \quad (27)$$

The ML estimate of the source signals is found by maximizing this function with respect to the unknown term $\mathbf{s}(t)$. The ML estimate is also the least squares estimate and is given by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}}(t) = (\mathbf{A}^H(\Theta) \mathbf{A}(\Theta))^{-1} \mathbf{A}^H(\Theta) \mathbf{x}(t) \quad (28)$$

and the estimator for $g(t)$ has the form:

$$\hat{g}(t) = \tilde{\mathbf{c}}^H (\mathbf{A}^H(\Theta) \mathbf{A}(\Theta))^{-1} \mathbf{A}^H(\Theta) \mathbf{x}(t). \quad (29)$$

This is a linear estimator, therefore the optimal beamformer weights are :

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{ML}} = \mathbf{A}(\Theta) (\mathbf{A}^H(\Theta) \mathbf{A}(\Theta))^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{c}}. \quad (30)$$

The ML estimator makes minimal assumptions about the source signal waveforms, but requires perfect knowledge of all the source DOA's, including those of the interferers, which are generally not known. With this information, the beamformer weights are determined exactly and cannot be implemented adaptively because there is no term which can be derived from the received signals, as was the case with the two MMSE estimators.

B. UNKNOWN (NON-RANDOM) DOA's & COVAR.

When some or all of the desired signal DOA's or waveform structures are not known, we cannot use the classical nulling techniques of Howells-Applebaum, Frost, and LMS, and when the desired signal DOA's, covariance matrix, and/or interference signal DOA's are unknown, we cannot implement the estimator/beamformers presented in the previous three sections. We can, however, reformulate the known-parameter waveform estimation problem into an unknown-parameter waveform estimation problem.

Let ξ represent the unknown parameters. If we assume that the source signals are Gaussian random processes, and ξ is a set of unknown, non-random parameters, we are faced with an ill-posed problem for which no meaningful waveform estimators can be found, primarily because there are too many unknowns. Instead, we can collect received signal samples and use this "training data" to estimate the unknown parameters, which may then be used in the MMSE signal estimators which are informed of the parameter values. ML estimates of the unknown parameters under these assumptions are found from [9]:

$$\hat{\xi}_{\text{ML}} = \arg \max - \log \det [\mathbf{R}_x(\xi)] - \text{tr} [\mathbf{R}_x^{-1}(\xi) \hat{\mathbf{R}}_x] \quad (31)$$

When substituted into the "informed" estimators ((18) and (24)), the resulting estimators are not optimal but may be close to optimal when the parameter estimates are very good.

If we assume that the source signals have unknown, non-random waveforms, we can find joint ML estimates of the unknown DOA's and signal waveforms. The ML estimates for the DOA's are found from ([9]):

$$\hat{\Theta}_{\text{ML}} = \arg \max \text{tr} [\mathbf{A}(\Theta) (\mathbf{A}^H(\Theta) \mathbf{A}(\Theta))^{-1} \mathbf{A}^H(\Theta) \hat{\mathbf{R}}_x] \quad (32)$$

and the signal waveform estimates have the same form as in the known parameter case (28), with the estimates of the unknown signal locations taking the place of the unknown parameters.

Alternately, we can assume that the unknown parameters are random variables with a known joint pdf. Under these assumptions we can find both MMSE and MAP signal estimators, which are presented in the next two sections.

38.5.4

C.1 MMSE ESTIMATOR - RANDOM DOA's

We use the same formulation as in Section A.1, with the additional assumptions that the desired and interference signal DOA's and covariance matrices are unknown, independent random variables with known joint pdf, $p(\xi)$, where we use the symbol ξ to denote the collection of unknown parameters. The MMSE estimate of $g(t)$ is the expected value of $\hat{g}(t)$ from Equation (18), with the expectation taken over all values of ξ :

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{g}(t) &= \int E[g(t)|\xi, \mathbf{x}(u); 0 \leq u \leq t] p[\xi | \mathbf{x}(u); 0 \leq u \leq t] d\xi \\ &= \int E[g(t)|\xi, \mathbf{x}(t)] p[\xi | \mathbf{x}(u); 0 \leq u \leq t] d\xi \\ &= \int \mathbf{w}_{MM}(\xi) \mathbf{x}(t) p[\xi | \mathbf{x}(u); 0 \leq u \leq t] d\xi \\ &= \mathbf{w}_{MM}(\xi) \mathbf{x}(t)\end{aligned}\quad (33)$$

where

$$\mathbf{w}_{MM}(\xi) = \int \mathbf{w}_{MM}(\xi) p[\xi | \mathbf{x}(u); 0 \leq u \leq t] d\xi \quad (34)$$

is the expected value of $\mathbf{w}_{MM}(\xi)^H$ given all of the past values of the received signals. The optimal weight vector is given by:

$$\mathbf{w}_{RMSE} = \mathbf{w}_{MM}(\xi). \quad (35)$$

Computing these weights involves solving the integral in Equation (34), which may not have a closed form solution and may have to be solved numerically. Furthermore, the weights are adaptive in the sense that they change as more and more past samples of the received signals are used the computation, but the adaptation procedure is not as straightforward as in the known-parameter cases.

C.2 MAP ESTIMATOR - RANDOM DOA's

We use the same formulation as in the previous section and find the MAP estimate of $g(t)$ by first finding the joint MAP estimate of $s(t)$ and ξ . The a posteriori pdf of $s(t)$ and ξ can be expanded as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}p[s(t), \xi | \mathbf{x}(u); 0 \leq u \leq t] &= p[s(t) | \xi, \mathbf{x}(u); 0 \leq u \leq t] p[\xi | \mathbf{x}(u); 0 \leq u \leq t] \\ &= p[s(t) | \xi, \mathbf{x}(t)] p[\xi | \mathbf{x}(u); 0 \leq u \leq t].\end{aligned}\quad (36)$$

If we first hold ξ constant and maximize over $s(t)$, we get the conditional mean:

$$\hat{s}(t) = \mathbf{R}_s(\xi) \mathbf{A}(\Theta) \mathbf{R}_s^{-1}(\xi) \mathbf{x}(t). \quad (37)$$

where

$$\mathbf{R}_s(\xi) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_D & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{R}_I \end{bmatrix} \quad (38)$$

and $\mathbf{R}_s(\xi) = \mathbf{A}(\Theta) \mathbf{R}_s(\xi) \mathbf{A}(\Theta)^H + \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}$. Substituting (37) into (36) and simplifying, the MAP estimate of ξ is found from:

$$\hat{\xi}_{MAP} = \arg \max \frac{\det[\mathbf{R}_s(\xi)]}{\det[\mathbf{R}_s(\xi)]} p[\xi | \mathbf{x}(u); 0 \leq u \leq t] \quad (39)$$

Therefore, the MAP estimate of $g(t)$ and the optimal weight vector are given by:

$$\hat{g}(t) = \mathbf{w}_{MM}(\hat{\xi}) \mathbf{x}(t). \quad (40)$$

and

$$\mathbf{w}_{RMAP} = \mathbf{w}_{MM}(\hat{\xi}). \quad (41)$$

To compute the random parameter MAP weights, we must first evaluate (38), which may be difficult in general. Again, the weights are adaptive in the sense that they change as more and more past samples of the received signals are used to estimate ξ . It is interesting to note that the MAP estimator chooses the most likely set of DOA's and uses them in the "informed" estimator (18), while the MMSE estimator computes a weighted average of "informed" estimators. Both estimators are computationally complex and do not appear to have simple hardware or numerical implementations.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we reformulated the adaptive nulling problem as a signal estimation problem and derived several adaptive nulling algorithms which require varying amounts of a priori information about the desired signals. We first assumed that desired signal DOA's and covariance were known and derived MMSE, MAP, constrained MMSE, and ML estimators. Furthermore, we showed that the classical adaptive nulling techniques of Howells and Applebaum, LMS, and Frost were equivalent to the optimal signal estimators derived. Next we assumed that the desired signal DOA's and covariance were unknown or partially known non-random parameters. In this case we had to estimate the unknown parameters from training data and substitute the estimates into the optimal (informed) signal estimators. Finally we considered DOA's which were unknown random variables whose a priori probability density functions were known, for which we derived MMSE and MAP estimators. Each of the estimators was linear and could be implemented as an adaptive nulling beamformer.

When the adaptive nulling problem is reformulated as an estimation problem, there are endless variations on the estimator/beamformers which can be obtained by changing our assumptions, and each allows more flexibility for incorporating any a priori knowledge we may have about the system.

VI. REFERENCES

1. S. W. W. Shor, "Adaptive Technique to Discriminate Against Coherent Noise in a Narrow-Band System", *J. Acoust. Soc. Amer.*, Vol. 39, Jan. 1966.
2. S. P. Applebaum, "Adaptive Arrays", Syracuse University Research Corporation Report SPL TR 66-1, Aug. 1966.
3. S. P. Applebaum, "Adaptive Arrays", *IEEE Trans. AP*, Vol. 24, Sept. 1976.
4. P. W. Howells, "Explorations in Fixed and Adaptive Resolution at GE and SURC", *IEEE Trans. AP*, Vol. 24, Sept. 1976.
5. B. Widrow, P. E. Mantley, L. J. Griffiths, and B. B. Goode, "Adaptive Antenna Systems", *Proc. IEEE*, Vol. 55, Dec. 1967.
6. O. L. Frost, III, "An Algorithm for Linearly Constrained Adaptive Array Processing", *Proc. IEEE*, Vol. 60, Aug. 1972.
7. L. J. Griffiths, "A Simple Adaptive Algorithm for Real-Time Processing in Antenna Arrays", *Proc. IEEE*, Vol. 57, Oct. 1969.
8. R. T. Compton, *Adaptive Antennas*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall, 1988.
9. J. F. Bohme, "Separated Estimation of Wave Parameters and Spectral Parameters by Maximum Likelihood", in *Proc. 1986 Int. Conf. on ASSP*, Tokyo, Japan, April 1986.